

THE ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND JOB SATISFACTION IN MEDIATING THE INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP STYLE ON LECTURERS' PERFORMANCE IN PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES IN KENDARI CITY

Dwi Zulfikar Mulyadi ^{1*}, Rahmat Madjid ², Hayat Yusuf ³ and Erwin Hadisantoso ⁴

¹ Student, Program Doctoral in Management Science, Halu Oleo University, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: [dwizulfikarm@gmail.com](mailto:dwitzulfikarm@gmail.com)

^{2,3,4} Lecturer, Program Doctoral in Management Science, Halu Oleo University, Indonesia.

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the role of organizational commitment and job satisfaction in mediating the influence of leadership style on lecturers' performance at private universities in Kendari City. The research design used was survey research (explanatory survey). The population in this study was all lecturers at accredited private universities in Kendari City, totaling 603 people, by calculating the sample size using the Slovin technique, resulting in a sample size of 240 people. The data analysis methods used in the research are descriptive analysis and inferential statistics, namely SEM based on Variance Partial Least Square (PLS). The results of this study indicate that transformational leadership style has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, transformational leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, transformational leadership style has a positive and insignificant effect on lecturer performance, transactional leadership style has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, transactional leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, transactional leadership style has a positive and insignificant effect on lecturer performance, organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on lecturer performance, job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on lecturer performance, organizational commitment plays a role in mediating the effect of transformational leadership style on lecturer performance, job satisfaction plays a role in mediating the effect of transformational leadership style on lecturer performance, organizational commitment plays a role in mediating the effect of transactional leadership style on lecturer performance and job satisfaction plays a role in mediating the effect of transactional leadership style on lecturer performance.

Keywords: Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Influence of Leadership Style and Lecturers' Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizations consist of people with formally assigned roles who work together to achieve organizational goals (Dessler, 2015). Every organization, both public institutions and business institutions, is required to carry out dynamic changes as a strategy to be able to adapt to the environment, so that the organization can survive and be sustainable (Sudarmanto 2009). The success and progress of an organization is determined by various key factors, including the active role of human resources (HR), which is an important asset to support the success of an organization. The importance of human resources needs to be realized by all levels of management in the organization. No matter how advanced technology is today, the human factor still plays an important role in the success of an organization (Mangkunegara, 2005).

One of the important steps that needs serious attention for organizational management is maintaining and improving employee performance. Performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance which means work achievement or actual work results achieved by someone. Performance is the work

results that can be achieved by employees in an organization, in accordance with the authority and responsibility given by the organization in an effort to achieve the vision, mission, and goals of the organization concerned legally, without violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics (Haris et al., 2014). Referring to Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, Lecturer performance is measured from the implementation of the tri dharma of higher education which includes education and teaching, research and community service. Several previous studies have shown that performance has a beneficial impact on organizations, such as increasing productivity. Employees who have good performance to work with full dedication make employees have the strength and desire to give more responsibility to support the welfare and success of the organization (Mayer 1991).

Leadership is the process of influencing others or the art of influencing human behavior, both individually and in groups (Thoha, 2013). Leadership in its application also has different styles. Leadership style is an effort or way for a leader to achieve organizational goals by considering the literal aspects, skills, traits, and attitudes of employees (Pradana 2013). Transformational leadership style according to (Yukl 2009) is defined through its impact on how leaders strengthen attitudes of mutual cooperation and trust, collective self-development, and team learning. Research conducted by Achmat Maskurochman (2020) and Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara (2016) found that transformational leadership style has a significant effect on performance. Research conducted by George Kay Kabiru (2020) and Setiani (2021) found that transactional leadership style has a significant effect on performance. Research conducted by Le Thi Minh Loan (2020) and Jufrizen (2018) found that organizational commitment has a significant effect on performance.

Job satisfaction is an important goal in human resource management (HR), because it will directly or indirectly affect work productivity. Ostroff (1992) stated that organizations that have more satisfied employees tend to be more effective than organizations that have fewer satisfied employees. Employee satisfaction and attitude are important factors in determining behavior and responses to work and through this behavior and response organizational effectiveness can be achieved (Handoko, 2000). Isyandi (2004), explains that job satisfaction is "a feeling that can please someone in working or that can provide fulfillment of work values". The relationship between job satisfaction and performance actually comes from Robbins' statement, "happy (satisfied) employees are productive employees" so it can be said that satisfied workers tend to want to be more involved in work so that they are more productive (Robbins, 2006). The measurement of job satisfaction variables in this research uses six indicators, namely, the work itself, salary, promotion opportunities, superiors, coworkers and working conditions (Luthans, 2006). Research conducted by Irina Yanchovska (2021) and Sabar Sutia (2022) found that job satisfaction has a significant effect on performance.

2. LITERATUR REVIEW

Leadership Style

Gary Yukl (2009) said that Leadership is the ability of an individual to influence, motivate, and enable others to contribute to the effectiveness and success of an organization. Wahjosumidjo (1994) stated that "Leadership is the activity of influencing

exercised to strive willingly for group objectives". Wahjosumidjo (1994) "Leadership is the exercises of authority and the making of decisions". Stonner (2003) "Leadership is a process of directing and influencing activities related to work and group members" from Stonner's opinion, an opinion can be drawn that leadership is an effort to influence and direct a group. Rivai (2014) stated that Leadership Style is a set of characteristics used by leaders to influence subordinates so that organizational goals are achieved or it can also be said that leadership style is a pattern of behavior and strategies that are preferred and often applied by a leader. Leadership style that shows, directly or indirectly, about a leader's belief in the ability of his subordinates means that leadership style is behavior and strategy, as a result of a combination of philosophy, skills, traits, attitudes, which are often applied by a leader when he tries to influence the performance of his subordinates. Furthermore, according to Stonner (1996) stated that leadership style is various behavioral patterns that are preferred by leaders in the process of directing and influencing workers.

Organizational Commitment

According to Strees (1997) organizational commitment reflects a sense of identification (belief in organizational values), involvement (willingness to do one's best for the sake of the organization) and loyalty (desire to remain a member of the organization in question). According to Allen and Meyer (1990) organizational commitment is a psychological construct that is a characteristic of the relationship between organizational members and their organization and has implications for individual decisions to continue their membership in the organization by reflecting affective orientations towards the organization, considerations of losses if leaving the organization, and moral burdens to continue in the organization. According to Luthans (2008) organizational commitment is a strong desire to remain a member of the organization. A desire to demonstrate high levels of effort on behalf of the organization and a strong belief in accepting the values and goals of the organization. According to Lambert and Hogan (2008) define organizational commitment as a form of a person's attachment to an organization. Gibson et al (2009) suggest that organizational commitment reflects a form of identification, loyalty and involvement expressed by employees towards the organization. According to Newsom and Davis (1989), employee organizational commitment is also known as employee loyalty, which is a level or degree of employee identification with the organization and their desire to continue their active participation in the organization.

Job Satisfaction

Luthans (2008), job satisfaction is the result of workers' perceptions of how their work provides something that is considered important. Robbins and Judge (2008) define job satisfaction as a positive feeling about one's work that is the result of evaluating its characteristics. (Isyandi, 2004) job satisfaction is a feeling that can please someone in working or that can provide fulfillment of work values. Fathoni (2006) job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves one's work. This attitude is reflected by work morale, discipline, and work performance. Meanwhile, according to (Wibowo, 2007) job satisfaction is a general attitude towards one's work that shows the difference between the amount of appreciation received by workers and the amount they believe they should receive. Mangkunegara (2009) states that job satisfaction is a feeling that supports or does not support employees related to their work and their condition. Feelings related to work involve aspects such as wages or salaries received,

career development opportunities, relationships with other employees, job placement, type of work, organizational structure, quality of supervision. Meanwhile, feelings related to oneself include age, health condition, ability and education.

Lecturer Performance

Performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance which means work achievement or actual work results achieved by a person. Performance is the work results that can be achieved by employees in an organization, in accordance with the authority and responsibility given by the organization in an effort to achieve the vision, mission, and goals of the organization concerned legally, without violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics (Haris et al., 2014). Rivai (2004) defines performance as real behavior displayed by each person as work achievements produced by employees according to their roles in (the organization). Simanjuntak (2005) defines performance as the level of achievement of results or implementation of certain tasks. Sedarmayanti (1996) defines (individual) performance as how a person carries out his work or work performance. The word work performance illustrates that individual performance can be seen from the enthusiasm or seriousness of the individual in carrying out the tasks assigned to him. Prawirosentono (1999) defines performance as the work results that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in order to achieve the goals of the organization in question legally, without violating the law and in accordance with norms or ethics. Mahmudi (2007) defines performance as the results of work (outcomes of work), because work results provide a strong link to the organization's strategic goals, customer satisfaction and economic contribution.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis

- H1: Transformational Leadership Style Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Organizational Commitment.
- H2: Transformational Leadership Style Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction.

- H3: Transformational Leadership Style Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Performance.
- H4: Transactional Leadership Style Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Organizational Commitment.
- H5: Transactional Leadership Style Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction.
- H6: Transactional Leadership Style Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Performance.
- H7: Organizational Commitment Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Performance.
- H8: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance.
- H9: The Role of Organizational Commitment in Mediating the Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Lecturer Performance Has a Positive and Significant Influence.
- H10: The Role of Job Satisfaction in Mediating the Effect of Transformational Leadership Style Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Lecturer Performance Has a Positive and Significant Influence.
- H11: The Role of Organizational Commitment in Mediating the Influence of Transactional Leadership Style on Lecturer Performance Has a Positive and Significant Influence.
- H12: The Role of Job Satisfaction in Mediating the Influence of Transactional Leadership Style on Lecturer Performance Has a Positive and Significant Influence.

3. METHODS

The population in this study was all lecturers at accredited private universities in Kendari City, totaling 603 people, by calculating the sample size using the Slovin technique, resulting in a sample size of 240 people. The data analysis methods used in the research are descriptive analysis and inferential statistics, namely SEM based on Variance Partial Least Square (PLS).

Operational Definition of Variables

Transformational leadership style (X1) is a leadership that pays attention to the problems faced by its followers. Transformational leadership is a leadership that pays attention to the needs and welfare of its lecturers. Leaders are able to increase the trust and confidence of lecturers so that they are motivated to do more than their jobs.

Transactional leadership style (X2) is a leader who guides or motivates their followers towards set goals by clarifying role and task requirements. Transactional leadership as a leadership model that involves an exchange process where followers receive immediate and tangible rewards after carrying out the leader's orders.

Organizational commitment (Y1) is the psychological bond, level of trust and acceptance of lecturers towards organizational goals which has implications for their decision to continue membership in the organization considering the losses if they

leave the organization and the moral responsibility to continue to remain in the organization.

Job satisfaction (Y2) is the emotional response (pleasant feeling) of lecturers towards their work and the conditions in the organization where they work.

Lecturer performance (Y3) is a description of the level of achievement in carrying out tasks which is shown through the quantity and quality of work results.

4. RESEARCH RESULT

Q-Square Value

Testing of the structural model is done by looking at the value of the coefficient of determination (R2) which is a test of the goodness of fit of the model. The R2 value can be presented in the table below:

Tabel 1: R-Square

Variable	R-Square
Transformational Leadership Style	
Transactional Leadership Style	
Organizational Commitment	0.634
Job Satisfaction	0.663
Lecturer Performance	0.547

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on table 1, the contribution of transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style variables to organizational commitment is 0.634 or 63.4% and to job satisfaction is 0.663 or 66.3%. The contribution of transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, organizational commitment and job satisfaction variables to lecturer performance is 0.547 or 54.7%. The R2 value of 0.547 indicates a moderate level of closeness, because it is between 0.50 - 0.75.

Predictive Relevance Value (Q2)

Predictive Relevance (Q2) for structural models, measures how well the observed values are generated by the model and also its parameter estimates. The Predictive Relevance (Q2) value is obtained using the blindfolding procedure which can be presented in the following table:

Tabel 2: Q-Square

Variable	Predictive Relevance (Q2)
Organizational Commitment	0.624
Job Satisfaction	0,654
Lecturer Performance	0,438

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Table 2 shows that the Predictive Relevance (Q2) value of organizational commitment is 0.624 or greater than 0.35, thus the constructs of transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style have great predictive relevance to organizational commitment. The Predictive Relevance (Q2) value of job satisfaction is 0.654 or greater than 0.35, thus the constructs of transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style have great predictive relevance to job satisfaction. The Predictive Relevance (Q2) value of lecturer performance is 0.438 or greater than 0.35,

thus the constructs of transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, organizational commitment and job satisfaction have great predictive relevance to lecturer performance.

Direct Influence

In the previous discussion it has been stated that in order to answer the problems and hypotheses proposed in this study, namely the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables, testing is carried out using smart PLS to determine the value of the path coefficient (path analysis). A summary of the results of the path analysis calculations in this study can be presented in the table below:

Table 3: Summary of Path Analysis Results

H	Research Variables		Path Coefficient	t-statistic	P-value	Information	
H-1	Transformational Leadership Style	→	Organizational Commitment	0.300	3.724	0,000	Accepted
H-2	Transformational Leadership Style	→	Job satisfaction	0.307	4.200	0.000	Accepted
H-3	Transformational Leadership Style	→	Lecturer Performance	0.091	1.042	0.298	Rejected
H-4	Transactional Leadership Style	→	Organizational Commitment	0.550	7.114	0.000	Accepted
H-5	Transactional Leadership Style	→	Job satisfaction	0.562	8.677	0.000	Accepted
H-6	Transactional Leadership Style	→	Lecturer Performance	0.096	1.105	0.269	Rejected
H-7	Organizational Commitment	→	Lecturer Performance	0.265	2.562	0.010	Accepted
H-8	Job satisfaction	→	Lecturer Performance	0.349	3.528	0.000	Accepted

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

Based on the results of the path analysis, it was found that transformational leadership style has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment and job satisfaction, each with a p-value of 0.000 and a path coefficient of 0.300 and 0.307. This indicates that an increase in transformational leadership style will increase organizational commitment and job satisfaction. However, the effect of transformational leadership style on lecturer performance is not significant with a p-value of 0.298 and a path coefficient of 0.091, so that an increase in transformational leadership style does not have a significant impact on lecturer performance.

Meanwhile, transactional leadership style also has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment and job satisfaction, with a p-value of 0.000 and a path coefficient of 0.550 and 0.562. However, like transformational leadership, the effect of transactional leadership on lecturer performance is also not significant, with a p-value of 0.269 and a path coefficient of 0.096.

Furthermore, organizational commitment and job satisfaction are proven to have a positive and significant effect on lecturer performance, with p-values of 0.010 and 0.000 respectively, and path coefficients of 0.265 and 0.349. This shows that increasing organizational commitment and job satisfaction will improve lecturer performance.

Indirect Influence (Mediation)

This study, in addition to analyzing the direct influence of exogenous and endogenous variables, also analyzes the indirect influence or through the mediation role of organizational commitment and job satisfaction variables in their influence between transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style on lecturer performance. The analysis of the mediation role path can be presented through the following table:

Table 4: Results of Indirect Influence Analysis (Mediation)

H	The Influence of Mediation			Path Coefficient	P-value	Information
	Exogenous Variables	Intervening Variables	Endogenous Variables			
H-9	Transformational Leadership Style	Organizational Commitment	Lecturer Performance	0.080	0.038	Accepted/ Perfect
H-10	Transformational Leadership Style	Job Satisfaction	Lecturer Performance	0.107	0.008	Accepted/ Perfect
H-11	Transactional Leadership Style	Organizational Commitment	Lecturer Performance	0.146	0.017	Accepted/ Perfect
H-12	Transactional Leadership Style	Job Satisfaction	Lecturer Performance	0.196	0.002	Accepted/ Perfect

Source: PLS Data Processing Results, 2023

5. DISCUSSION

The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Organizational Commitment

The results of the analysis show that transformational leadership style has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment of lecturers at private universities in Kendari. Transformational leadership style, which consists of the influence of idealism, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration, forms charismatic leader behavior and is able to increase lecturer commitment.

Leaders with individual consideration pay attention to the personal needs of lecturers and act as mentors, while intellectual stimulation encourages lecturers to think creatively and innovatively. Leaders with the influence of idealism act as role models, dare to take risks, and are consistent in morals and ethics. Leaders who have inspirational motivation are able to inspire and motivate lecturers to work better and achieve organizational goals.

This finding is in line with research by Tepi Peirisal (2022) and Naveeda K. Katpe (2020), which concluded that transformational leadership style has a positive effect on organizational commitment, supported by the theory that transformational leaders can adapt quickly to changes in the work environment and provide high motivation to employees, thereby increasing organizational commitment (Rivai, 2004).

The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction

The results of the study indicate that transformational leadership style has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction of lecturers at private universities in Kendari City. This leadership style is formed by the dimensions of the influence of idealism, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration. Transformational leaders are able to motivate lecturers, provide space for creativity, and pay attention to individual needs and welfare, so that lecturers feel happy and satisfied with their work. Leaders with the influence of idealism act as role models who are respected and followed, while intellectual stimulation encourages lecturers to be more creative and innovative. Inspirational motivation helps increase lecturers' self-confidence and encourages them to achieve better performance. In addition, transformational leaders pay attention to the personal needs of each lecturer, act as mentors, and listen to their complaints, thus creating a sense of satisfaction in their work. This is supported by research by Albert Puni (2018) and Abdel Wahhab (2022), which found that transformational leadership has a significant effect on job satisfaction. Supporting theories, such as those proposed by Keller (1992) and Andarika (2004), state that transformational leadership style can fulfill the needs of self-esteem and self-actualization, which ultimately increases job satisfaction. This research is also in line with the findings of Pambudi (2016), which states that appropriate leadership has a close relationship with employee job satisfaction.

The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Lecturer Performance

The results of the study indicate that transformational leadership style has a positive but insignificant effect on the performance of lecturers at private universities in Kendari City. Although this leadership style involves dimensions of idealism, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration, which encourage lecturers to admire, trust, and identify with their leaders, these findings indicate that individual attention given by leaders as mentors or counselors does not have a significant impact on improving lecturer performance. This is likely due to the nature of lecturer performance which is more independent and related to their main tasks in carrying out the Tri Dharma of higher education, such as education, research, and community service, which are measured through semester credit units (SKS). Although leaders provide motivation and support for creativity, individual responsibility in carrying out the Tri Dharma remains the main factor in lecturer performance. This study is supported by the findings of Retno Rafia (2020), who also found that transformational leadership style does not have a significant effect on performance, because leaders focus more on inspiring followers to put aside their individual interests (Robbins and Judge, 2015).

The Influence of Transactional Leadership Style on Organizational Commitment

Based on the results of the study, transactional leadership style has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment of lecturers in private universities in Kendari City. This leadership style involves contingent rewards, active exception management, and passive exception management, which effectively increase lecturers' commitment to the organization. Contingent rewards are given to lecturers who meet targets and comply with procedures, while active exception management involves direct supervision and correction of lecturer performance. In addition, passive exception management provides sanctions to lecturers who make mistakes, while providing rewards for those who successfully complete work according to standards.

These results indicate that transactional leadership style is able to motivate lecturers by providing rewards according to performance achievements and strict supervision, thereby increasing lecturers' emotional attachment to the organization. This finding is consistent with research by Naveed Iqbal Chaudhry (2020) and Denis (2021), which also found that transactional leadership style has a significant effect on organizational commitment. In accordance with the theories of Burns (1978) and Yukl (2010), transactional leadership involves an exchange process that generates enthusiasm and commitment from followers.

The Influence of Transactional Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction

The results of the study indicate that transactional leadership style has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction of lecturers at private universities in Kendari City. This leadership style involves contingent rewards, active exception management, and passive exception management, where leaders provide rewards in accordance with target achievement and comply with procedures, and directly supervise lecturers' performance. This supervision includes sanctions in the event of errors and rewards for good performance, which effectively motivates lecturers and increases job satisfaction. This transactional leadership style ensures that lecturers feel happy with work that matches their expertise, receive adequate income, and get fair promotion opportunities. This finding is in line with the research of Michael K. Mickson (2020) which states that transactional leadership has a significant effect on job satisfaction. Keller's theory (1992) also supports that transactional leadership is able to meet the basic needs of employees, such as physiological needs and a sense of security, which contributes to job satisfaction. This leadership clarifies roles and tasks, thereby increasing employee creativity and performance, which in turn increases job satisfaction (Gibson et al., 1997).

The Influence of Transactional Leadership Style on Lecturer Performance

The results of the study indicate that transactional leadership style has a positive but insignificant effect on the performance of lecturers at private universities in Kendari City. This leadership style involves contingent rewards, active exception management, and passive exception management, where leaders provide rewards according to target achievement and direct supervision of lecturers' performance. However, even though leaders promise rewards and carry out strict supervision, this does not have a significant impact on lecturer performance. This is due to the fact that the implementation of the Tri Dharma of higher education consisting of education, research, and community service is more individual and independent, so that lecturer performance is not fully influenced by transactional leadership style. This study is in line with the findings of Zhou Dongmei (2021) which states that transactional leadership style is not significant in improving performance, because this style focuses on the exchange relationship between leaders and subordinates (Mamesah, 2009).

The Influence of Organizational Commitment on Lecturer Performance

The results of the study indicate that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of lecturers at private universities in Kendari City. This commitment is formed by three main components: affective, normative, and ongoing commitment. Affective commitment is based on the emotional bond between lecturers and the organization, where lecturers feel that they have harmony between their life principles and organizational goals. Normative commitment arises from the moral awareness of lecturers to be loyal to the organization that has rendered them

many services. Meanwhile, ongoing commitment occurs because lecturers find it difficult to leave the organization due to the benefits and salaries received, as well as the fear of not finding another job that is equivalent. This high commitment can improve lecturer performance by strengthening their psychological bonds and trust in the organization.

This study is supported by the findings of Jufrizen (2018) and Le Thi Minh Loan (2020), as well as the theory of John Wiley & Sons, Inc. (1991), which states that individuals with high organizational commitment tend to have high performance. In addition, Robbins and Judge (2013) also stated that there is a strong relationship between organizational commitment and performance, where employees who are highly committed will show better loyalty and performance.

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Lecturer Performance

The results of the study indicate that job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on the performance of lecturers at private universities in Kendari City. This job satisfaction is formed by various factors such as working conditions, the job itself, salary, promotion opportunities, superiors, and coworkers. Lecturers who are satisfied with a clean work environment, work that suits their expertise, fair salary, fair promotion opportunities, support from leaders, and good relationships with coworkers tend to have better performance. This job satisfaction creates a positive emotional response that drives productivity.

This study is supported by the findings of Irina Yanchovska (2021) and Sabar Sutia (2022) who also found a significant influence between job satisfaction and performance. Robbins' theory (2008) states that satisfied workers are more productive because their involvement in work increases, while Wibowo (2014) states that good performance can also increase job satisfaction. In addition, Robbins and Timothy (2015) emphasize that organizations with more satisfied workers will be more effective in achieving goals.

The Role of Organizational Commitment in Mediating the Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Lecturer Performance

The results of the study indicate that organizational commitment plays a significant mediator in the influence of transformational leadership style on lecturer performance at private universities in Kendari City. Transformational leadership style, which involves charismatic behavior, motivation, and empowerment of lecturers to develop themselves through creativity and innovation, has a positive effect on lecturer performance. Organizational commitment, which is formed through the alignment between organizational goals and lecturers' life principles, strengthens the influence of leadership style on performance.

This study shows that organizational commitment perfectly mediates the influence of transformational leadership style, improving the performance of lecturers who feel comfortable in carrying out the tri dharma function. This finding is in line with research by Abd. Madjid (2021) and Mardiyana (2019), which found that organizational commitment positively and significantly mediates the influence of transformational leadership style on lecturer performance. Rivai's theory (2004) supports that transformational leaders always provide encouragement to their employees to complete tasks well, while Robbins and Judge (2013) emphasize that there is a strong relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance.

The Role of Job Satisfaction in Mediating the Effect of Transformational Leadership Style on Performance

The results of the study indicate that job satisfaction acts as a positive and significant mediator in the influence of transformational leadership style on lecturer performance at private universities in Kendari City. Transformational leadership style, which includes charismatic behavior, motivation, and self-development of lecturers through creativity and innovation, has a positive effect on lecturer performance. Job satisfaction, which is generated from factors such as salary, promotion opportunities, superior support, cooperative coworkers, and good working conditions, strengthens the influence of this leadership style. This study shows that job satisfaction perfectly mediates the relationship between transformational leadership style and lecturer performance. This finding is supported by research by Maya Rezeki Angriani (2020) and Achmad Sudiro (2020), which found a positive and significant effect of job satisfaction in mediating the influence of transformational leadership style on lecturer performance. In addition, Pambudi's theory (2016) states that a good and appropriate leadership style is closely related to employee job satisfaction, while Robbins (2008) states that satisfied employees tend to be more productive, which leads to increased performance.

The Role of Organizational Commitment in Mediating the Influence of Transactional Leadership Style on Lecturer Performance

The results of the study indicate that organizational commitment acts as a positive and significant mediator in the influence of transactional leadership style on lecturer performance at private universities in Kendari City. Transactional leadership style, which involves an exchange process in which lecturers receive direct rewards after carrying out tasks in accordance with specified procedures and targets, has a positive effect on lecturer performance. Organizational commitment influences this relationship by ensuring the congruence between organizational goals and lecturers' life principles. If organizational goals are in line with lecturers' values, then commitment and desire to continue working in the organization remain high. This study is supported by Owin Jamasy (2019) and Karwan Hamasalih Qadir (2020), who found that the role of organizational commitment in mediating the influence of transactional leadership style on lecturer performance was positive and significant. In addition, Yukl's theory (2010) explains that transactional leadership style can generate enthusiasm and commitment, while John Wiley & Sons (1991) state that individuals with high organizational commitment tend to have high performance and are proud to be part of the organization.

The Role of Job Satisfaction in Mediating the Influence of Transactional Leadership Style on Lecturer Performance

The results of the study indicate that job satisfaction acts as a positive and significant mediator in the influence of transactional leadership style on lecturer performance at private universities in Kendari City. The transactional leadership style applied, with a clear exchange process and directive supervision, increases lecturer job satisfaction through appropriate rewards and opportunities for promotion, as well as support from leaders and colleagues. This job satisfaction plays an important role in influencing the performance of lecturers, who feel comfortable in carrying out the tri dharma function. This study is supported by Siswanto (2020) who found that organizational commitment significantly mediates the influence of transactional leadership style on lecturer

performance. In addition, Keller (1992) explains that transactional leadership style can increase job satisfaction by meeting basic employee needs, such as physiological needs and a sense of security. Robbins and Timothy (2015) also stated that organizations with more satisfied workers tend to be more effective than organizations with few satisfied workers.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that transformational and transactional leadership styles have a positive influence on organizational commitment and job satisfaction of lecturers, but are not directly significant on lecturer performance. Transformational leadership style is able to increase organizational commitment and job satisfaction through motivation, inspiration, and individual attention, although its impact on lecturer performance is not significant due to the nature of independence in implementing the tri dharma function. Meanwhile, transactional leadership style, which involves the exchange of rewards based on achievement, also increases organizational commitment and job satisfaction of lecturers significantly, although it does not have a significant direct impact on lecturer performance. Organizational commitment and job satisfaction act as mediators that strengthen the influence of leadership style on lecturer performance, by providing a sense of comfort in carrying out teaching duties. Overall, organizational commitment and job satisfaction have an important role in mediating the influence of leadership style on lecturer performance.

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